

DESIGN AND TESTING OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITES FOR FLYWHEEL ROTOR

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ABSTRACT

An attempt was made to apply carbon fiber reinforced three-dimensional composites (3D-CF) to a high speed rotation disk aiming at enhancing the burst tip speed of the disk by placing reinforcements in three directions r , θ and z of the cylindrical coordinate. It was shown by finite element calculations that 3D-CF is advantageous for high speed rotation due to capability of fabricating a disk having low outer to inner radius ratio (D_r), 0.5 or below. Thus, 3D-fabrics for a prototype rotor with D_r of 0.14 were produced, and three specific methods for joining the 3D-CF to a hub were designed and evaluated by spin test.

1 INTRODUCTION

The flywheel is one of promising energy storage systems. The energy stored in a flywheel increases with the square of the product of a radius (r) and rotation speed (ω). Thus, the enhancement of the maximum tip speed (equal to $r\omega$) has been one of the main targets of existing studies. The burst tip speed of a rotating disk is dominated by the specific tensile strength of constituent material. Hence High-specific-strength carbon-fiber-reinforced-plastics (CFRPs) have been applied to high-speed rotors [1].

Dominant stresses induced in a disk under high-speed rotation are radial tensile stress (σ_r) and circumferential tensile stress (σ_θ), among which σ_θ is the highest. Hence, fiber bundles have generally been placed along the circumferential direction (θ) in existing studies [1]. Stress distribution in a rotating disk with a center hole depends on the ratio of inner to outer radius ($D_r = D_i/D_o$; Small D_r means small hole). When D_r becomes small, σ_r tends to increase. Thus, the circumferentially wound composites disk often suffers premature radial delamination along the fiber [2].

To prevent the delamination, multi-ring method has been adopted [3-5]. In this method multiple thin rings of CFRP are assembled by press-fit. Thus in a multi-ring rotor, σ_r can be kept negative, and this compressive stress suppresses the delamination. However, a multi-ring disk with D_r smaller than 0.5 has never been fabricated for high-speed rotation, because radial fiber reinforcement is indispensable for such an occasion. To this ends, the burst tip speed of the multi-ring rotors has been less than approximately 1,000m/s.

A CFRP disk requires a metal hub to be connected to a spindle and assembled into a flywheel system. Because burst tip speed of metals is much smaller than that of CFRPs, the diameter of a metal hub should be small. Thus, a CFRP disk having small D_r is advantageous for high-speed rotation.

In the present study, a new approach using 3-dimensionally carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic (3D-CF) is proposed for enhancement of the rotation speed of a disk. The fiber reinforcement in the r direction of the 3D-CF can avoid the circumferential delamination. The fiber reinforcement in the axial direction

enables the thickness to vary from inner to outer edge. On the basis of these advantages, a prototype model was designed, fabricated, and experimentally examined by spin test.

2 Analysis

The burst tip-speeds of existing disks and a 3D-CF disk were estimated using finite element calculations to demonstrate advantages of the 3D-CF disk.

2.1 3-dimensional fabric and boundary conditions

Figure 1 shows a 3D-fabric in which reinforcements are aligned in three directions r , θ and z of the cylindrical coordinate. Thus, the 3D-CF disk exhibits orthotropic properties with nine independent values. Elastic properties and strengths of the 3D-CF disk were estimated using equivalent inclusion method [6]. High strength type PAN-based-carbon-fiber (TORAYCA T1000G, Toray Japan) was assumed in calculations. Table 1 shows Physical and elastic properties of carbon fiber, matrix resin and Ti alloy. The total volume fraction of fiber in the 3D-CF ($V_t = V_{fr} + V_{f\theta} + V_{fz}$) was assumed to be 55%, where V_{fr} , $V_{f\theta}$ and V_{fz} denote volume fraction of the fiber in the respective cylindrical coordinate components. The calculation was repeated searching for the optimal design for the highest rotation speed under the following restrictions.

- 1) V_{fz} is 5%.
- 2) $V_{f\theta}$ is constant within the radius.
- 3) The sum of V_{fr} and $V_{f\theta}$ is 50%.

Figure 1 Schematic running patterns of fiber bundles in the cylindrically orthogonal fabric.

In this study, the outer diameter of the disk (D_o) was assumed to be 300mm, the height along the inner radius 20mm. D_r was varied by changing the inner diameter.

Two types of 3D-CF disks, 3D-CF-A and 3D-CF-B, were considered. The 3D-CF-A has a constant thickness of 20mm, and the 3D-CF-B has variable thickness. For attaining high strength, the continuity of reinforcing fiber is imperative. Carbon fiber bundles running in the θ direction are drawn as concentric circles in figure 1, but in actual fabrics, the θ bundle was continuous, and was shifted to the neighboring outer circle after running one circle like a filament-winding process. In order to satisfy this condition, all disks have constant number of bundles in the radial direction. Thus, the 3D-CF-A has V_{fr} inversely proportional to the radial position (r). Once V_{fr} is fixed at inner radius, $V_{f\theta}$ is determined from the condition of 3). The 3D-CF-B keeps a constant V_{fr} at any radial position (r) because its thickness was varied in the fashion inversely proportional to r . Hence, from the condition of 3), $V_{f\theta}$ was also set to be a constant value.

The hub connecting a disk and shaft was assumed to be Ti (Ti-6Al-4V), because specific strength of Ti is stronger than other metals.

For the purpose of comparison, the burst tip speeds of two types of conventional rings were also evaluated; i.e., unidirectionally reinforced composite disks in which carbon fiber is wound only in the circumferential direction (UD-CFs) and press-fit disks in which two concentric rings was assembled by compressive force (MR-CFs). The V_s of the UD-CFs and MR-CFs were assumed to be 60%. Analysis was carried out using the commercial finite element code, ABAQUS Version 6.6. Figure 2 illustrates an axi-symmetry model for the 3D-CF-B. This mesh size was of about 1mm maximum on a side. Material properties unique to its radial position were allotted to each element. Burst tip speed (BTS) was evaluated using the maximum stress criterion, where fracture is assumed to occur when stress reached 75 % of the tensile strength.

Figure 2 Finite element model used for determination of stress distribution in the 3D-CF-B disk.

Material	Mass density	Longitudinal elastic modulus	Transverse elastic modulus	Poisson's ratio		Tensile strength
	ρ (kg/m ³)	E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_{LT}	ν_{TT}	(MPa)
T1000G	1800 ^a	294 ^a	40 ^b	0.31 ^b	0.33 ^b	6370 ^a
Epoxy	1250	3.4	-	0.36	-	NA
Ti-6Al-4V	4500	112	-	0.3	-	800

a Toray carbon fiber America, T1000G data sheet

b (from [6])

Table 1 Physical and elastic properties of carbon fiber, matrix resin and Ti alloy

2.2 Analytical results

Figure 3 shows calculation results of BTS of the composite disks and Ti-hub as a function of D_r . It follows from this figure that introduction of the 3D-CF-B improves BTS compared with the UD-CF and MR-CF. In general, σ_θ increases with the increase in D_r , and σ_r increases with the decrease in D_r . Hence, a UD-CF with low D_r should have a low BTS because of extremely low tensile strength in the radial direction. Thus, the UD-CF is advantageous only when D_r is larger than 0.8. The MR-CF improves this shortcoming in the range around $D_r=0.5$ to 0.8, and enhance burst tip speed up to about 1,000m/s.

In Figure 3, the burst tip speed of the 3D-CF-A is predicted to drop when D_r is smaller than 0.4. On the other hand, BTS of the 3D-CF-B is enhanced when D_r becomes even smaller than 0.2. This behavior is due to high thickness of the 3D-CF-B at near center of the disk. The thick inner region sustains the load transferred from outer region by high centrifugal force. It should be noted in Figure 3 that BTS of 1,700m/s is predicted for the 3D-CF-B, and this is higher than that of any existing rotors.

Next, let us discuss BTS taking the fracture of the Ti-hub into account. In Figure 3, intersection of two curves of a composite disk and the Ti-hub indicates that the fracture occurs simultaneously in both of them. The three intersections of the Ti-hub and the composites, UD-CF, 3D-CF-A, and 3D-CF-B are D_r equal to 0.78, 0.55, and 0.5, respectively. When D_r is higher than these values, the Ti-hub fracture should occur before composite fracture. Hence, fracture of Ti-hub is likely suppressed when the MR-CF disk is used compared with the UD-CF having the same value of D_r . However, when the 3D-CF-B is adopted, the fracture of Ti-hub can be prevented in a wide range of D_r .

Figure 3 Burst tip speed (BTS) of composites and Ti-hub as a function of D_r .

3 Design of 3D-CF rotor system

3.1 Disk design

We conducted a trial fabrication of the 3D-CF-B using T1000G-12k, in which fiber bundles were arranged under the conditions of $V_{fr}+V_{f\theta}=0.45$, $V_{fz}=0.02$, and $D_r=0.14$. In this 3D-CF-B, V_{fr} and $V_{f\theta}$ were optimized, respectively, at 0.186 and 0.264. In Figure 4, the shape of the trial disk is shown: the thickness region near the inner radius is used for joining to the spindle.

The configuration of the prototype 3D-CFRP disk is shown in Figure 4. This disk has an outer diameter of 305mm and inner diameter of 40mm. The thicknesses at several radii of the disk (t) were set following the optimum condition determined by the calculation; namely $t=12\text{mm}$ at $r=31\text{mm}$, $t=6.3\text{mm}$ at $r=79$, and $t=4\text{mm}$ at the outer radius, and linearly connecting these thickness along the in-between radii.

Figure 5 presents a comparison of the distributions of V_{fr} and $V_{f\theta}$ in the trial disk and those of optimized values as functions of normalized radius (r/D_o). In this figure, a photograph of the trial fabric was also shown. The BTS and energy density of this 3D-CF-B including the hub were calculated, respectively, as 1520 m/s and 121 Wh/kg.

3D fabrics (SIKIBO Inc., Japan) was used for the prototype rotor.

Figure 4 Trail disk of 3D-CF-B for type I.

Figure 5 Comparison of distributions of V_{fr} and $V_{f\theta}$ in a trial 3D-CF-B with those of optimized values.

3.2 Interface with metal hub

Under the disk rotation, the inner radius of a 3D-CF disk expands more than the outer radius of a hub because of the centrifugal forces. This tendency is enhanced when D_r decreases because, when D_r becomes smaller, the integrated centrifuge force working on a disk becomes much stronger than that on the hub. Consequently, the disk and the hub tend to detach under a high-speed rotation.

Maintaining the joining a rotation disk made of 3D-CF to an Al hub is a problem to be solved.

In order to avoid the separation of the two parts under high rotation, three types of measures were examined.

Figure 6 shows the test fixtures of type I spin test. The concept of the method in which two surfaces are in contact during rotation are shown as follows. The outer surface of the central cylindrical of 3D-CF as shown in Figure 4 was press-fitted into the inner surface of the flange of a Cap hub in Fig. 6. By changing the ring part thickness from inner to outer radius of the flange, the deformation by rotation of two surfaces in contact with each other can equal out. This equalization results in no interaction from each other's surface, therefore leaving the initial pressure induced by press-fit unchanged and making the connection stable.

Figure 6 Test fixtures of type I spin test.

Figure 7 shows test fixtures of type II spin test. This type has been used for spin test up to tip speed of 500m/s [7]. In order to improve the contact-keeping speed possible, the following was proposed. A hub is shrink-fitted to a 3D-CF. As the angular velocity increases, a 3D-CF tend to more expand outward and causes a separation. A 3D-CF disk has a tapered angle of 5 degree on the underside of the disk shown in Fig.7 (b). A tapered ring has also a tapered angle of 5 degree on its top face parallel to that of the 3D-CF. The tapered ring is thrusting upward by disk spring force and sliding along the tapered surface. This upward motion of the tapered ring adjusts the disk center to the hub center. A 3D-CF disk rotates and is held between the hub and the tapered ring.

Figure 7 Test fixtures of type II spin test; (a) setting of the specimen, (b) Type II 3D-CF disk.

Figure 8 shows test fixtures of type III spin test. The specimen constitutes of three parts, a disk, a hub and a Polyoxymethylene (POM) ring. Polymer materials have a high thermal expansion coefficient compared with metals. The amount of shrink fit depends on the thermal expansion of the material to be inserted and determine the speed at which a separation occurs. POM (CP-15X, POLYPLASTIC CO.,LTD) has the thermal expansion coefficient of 110 ($\mu\epsilon/K$). It is four times larger than that of Al alloy. This means separation speed doubles using POM as the hub, because the deformation of the rotating disk is in linear to the square of angular velocity. In figure 8, a metal hub was press-fitted after POM ring's shrink fit.

Figure 8 Test fixtures of a new spin test using POM ring between 3D-CF and hub.

4 SPIN TEST

Figure 9 shows schematic diagram of the spin tester. Spin test was conducted to evaluate the performance of the prototype rotors using a spin tester (Maruwa Electronic Inc., Japan) driven by an

air turbine. The pressure in a chamber that prototype rotor was set in was reduced to 80Pa. A displacement gauge was installed at the arbor to observe shaft vibration. The rotation speed was increased by a rate of 100rpm/s.

Three type specimens are being tested up to the tip speed; Type I : 510m/s, Type II: 530m/s, Type III: 800m/s.

Figure 9 Schematic diagram of the spin tester

5 CONCLUSIONS

It was found from results of finite element calculations that 3D-CF disks with D_r less than 0.45 have a burst tip speed more than 1,500m/s. Based on this calculation a prototype rotor was fabricated and spin tests were performed. As of today, the maximum tip speed of type III disk was 800m/s.

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